

Abstract:

Testing is traditional method of checking out and improving software quality. This paper explains the Testing process, how bugs are tracked and logged, and combination of testing techniques, documents and formats required. Basic rationale is executing software in controlled manner to determine whether it performs according to customer satisfaction. It is important to have an understanding of relative criticality of defects, when planning test, reporting status and recommending actions.

Software engineers build a tangible project from abstract concept; series of test cases are developed with an intension to demote the software. Testing is destructive rather than constructive. However, the objective is constructive.

1. Introduction

Testing is a critical activity in quality assurance, requiring ample time and sufficient planning. *Quality is the conformance to requirements. Software quality is not relevant to feasibility. Testing is not done to improve software accuracy. If requirements are changing continuously, then work with the project's stakeholders early on to understand how requirements might change so that alternate test plans and strategies can be worked out in advance, if possible. We can also negotiate to allow only easily-implemented new requirements into the project, while moving more difficult new requirements into future versions of the application. The goal of testing is bug fixing of errors in requirement analysis, design and coding phase. Primary goal is bug prevention and secondary goal is bug discovery. The main objective of testing to find faults in the software, to test whether the software is ready for release and to demonstrate that the software does not work as per requirements. However, to prove that the software has no*

faults and debugging the defects is not a testing objective. The objective of the test is an important criterion in deciding what testing technique to be used. Faults found by the user are due to poor software quality and poor testing. Undetected errors may lead to faults and eventually to incorrect behavior. A fault discovered in requirements and later in the development cycle is more expensive to fix as the fault has already been built in to documents, code and tests. The main reason for testing before release of software is to take decision before a risk based software release. Use risk based analysis to find out which areas need to be tested, if the project isn't big enough to justify extensive testing. Testing should start as soon as possible in SDLC. Increasing the quality of software by better development methods, reduces the test phases and time needed for testing. So if we find a lot of bugs in testing, we should not be too confident about the software quality. In development activities, errors are introduced due to logical errors, careless or improper communication, and need to rush through the whole process of software development. The best procedure for testing in SDLC is early test analysis and design and also designing different levels of tests to cover specific test objectives and purposes. Testability of the requirements and system are a part of test analysis and design. Early test design can find faults, prevent fault multiplication and also cause changes in requirements. Test basis comprise of requirements, architecture, design, interfaces. Evaluating the test basis is a part of test analysis and design phase. SDLC follows plan, do check, act principle. The cost of faults is the cheapest to find in the early development phase and the most expensive to fix in the latest test phase. Testing should start as soon as the software requirements have been approved. Early testing, defect clustering and pesticide paradox are all testing principle. However, exhaustive testing is not a testing principle. Fundamental test processes include planning and control, test closure activities, analysis and design. Checking

which planned deliverables have been delivered, finalizing and archiving testware and analyzing lessons are part of test closure activities but not defect report analysis. Deliverables of test design phase includes test data, test data plan and test procedure. Hand over is typically a process which is part of test closure activities. After closure of test cycle test-ware is handover to the maintenance organization.

Therefore, testing is conducted to uncover and reduce those errors. When ever a piece of software is received by the testers, they should test the areas most critical to business processes and also test the areas where faults will be maximum. At times, if the software is not ready for production we call it as “Having to say NO”. Commercial off the shelf software is called as COTS.

2.1. What is the difference between error, failure, defect and bug?

*Errors are mistakes occurred by the developer while coding. If error occurs then system will not perform as per client specification so it fails. When the tester finds that that the system cannot function to give the expected result, then from the tester’s point of view it is a defect. When what is visible to the end user is a deviation from the specific or expected behavior. It is called as a defect. When the developer confirms that the defect is a valid issue it is called as a bug from developer’s point of view. **The number of defects identified in a component or system divided by the size of the component or the system is called as defect density.***

One key reason why developers have difficulty testing their own work is due to lack of objectivity. Fault masking is error condition hiding another error condition.

2.2. What are Bugs? What is Debugging?

Bugs are errors found during execution of program, which is introduced due to logical or syntactical faults. Bugs can be software bug or hardware bug. Some bugs may be deferred or postponed for locking in subsequent release of the software. These bugs are called ‘Deferred

Bugs. *Debugging* is the process of locating, understanding and removing bugs during software failure. Debugging supports testing but cannot replace them. No amount of testing is sufficient to grantee 100% error free software. ***De-bugging is least important in test management. Adding known defects by seeding is called as be-bugging.***

2.3. Severity and Priority of Bugs

Severity indicates how serious the bug is. It reflects the impact on products and customers of the product.

Critical severity: System crash, data loss, data corruption.

Major severity: Operational errors, wrong results, loss of functionality.

Minor severity: Defect in user interface layout, spelling mistakes.

Priority indicates how important it is to fix the bug and when it should be fixed.

Immediate Priority: Bugs blocking further testing and is very visible.

At the earliest Priority: Bug must be fixed at the earliest before the product is released.

Normal Priority: Bug should be fixed if time permits.

Later Priority: Bug may be fixed, but can be released as it is.

Example: Classification of bugs as per their severity and priority.

Bug Type	Severity	Priority
Data corruption bug that happens very rarely.	Critical	Normal
Release of software, for testing that crashes as soon as you start it out.	Critical	Immediate
A button should be moved a little further down the page	Minor	Later

3. Steps for testing software

→ **Smoke Testing** / **Confidence testing** / Sanity Testing / Gorilla Testing / Qualification

Testing

- Ad-hoc Testing
- Write test cases from Functional Requirement Specification (FRS)
- Executing test cases manually (**Module Testing**)
- Logging / Reporting Bugs through Bug Tracking life cycle
- Regression testing done to ensure stable position of software
- Test Automation
- Integration / Interface Testing
- **System Testing**
- **User Acceptance** testing:

Test estimation effort is required to perform activities. For writing user acceptance test cases, we use the output of the requirement analysis, the requirement specification is used as the input. Test control is used for reallocation of resources. Requirement Analysis is not a phase of fundamental test process. Test monitoring has measures of tracking process. Percentage of test case execution, percentage of work done in test environment preparation, defect information e.g. defect density, defects found and fixed helps in monitoring the test progress. However it does not depend on the size of the testing team and skills of engineers. An expert based test estimation technique is called as Wide band Delphi. Characteristics of User Acceptance Testing includes testing performed by users, testing against acceptance test criteria. Integration of system with user documentation, no use of automated test execution tools.

In **Smoke testing** each time, the software team gets the latest version of the software; an initial test is done to check whether the built is stable enough. It *is testing major functionalities*, to

verify whether the software is stable and performs effectively and can be considered for future test efforts.

Ad-hoc testing is a creative informal test based on formal test cases, thus need not be documented by testing team. Tests are random, based on error guessing ability and business knowledge. Test includes initial and later stages.

Regression testing is done when a change is made in source code or a change is made in the environment, or a new module is added as a part of integration testing, i.e. the developer fixes any defect. Set of predefined test cases is checked to determine whether any unchanged portions of the software are affected or they are working fine, whether bugs are re-occurring or fixed properly. The selection of test cases for regression testing requires knowledge on the bug fixes and how it affects the system, includes the area of frequent defects and also includes the area which has undergone many/recent code changes. Introducing a small change to the program and having the effects of that change show up in some test is called as 'mutation'. Capture / Playback is a tool involved in automation of regression testing. It is also used in performance testing, recovery testing, GUI testing but least used in user requirement testing. A typical commercial test execution tool would be able to compare of expected outcomes with actual outcomes, recording test inputs, reading test values from a data file except calculating expected outputs. Change control is most vital in assessing the impact of proposed software modifications.

Regression testing may be done manually. Regression testing benefits the most from the use of this test tool. They are used to support multi-user testing, which capture aspects of user behavior and are the most frequently purchased type of case tools.

Regression testing is different from Re-testing/ Confirmation testing. In Re-testing, the same test case is executed again due to unexpected behavior of the program, encountered by the tester. Re-testing ensures the original fault has been removed. The tester may cause the test case to fail and raise a defect. After the developer fixes the defect, the tester again executes the same test case to check whether the test case is working fine. Metrics from previous similar projects and discussion with the development team helps us in estimating the amount of re-testing likely to be required. Some times the fix may introduce a new defect in the software. So a tester does regression testing to discover the bug and look for unexpected side effects in the system. System testing is to be performed, which includes business process based testing, requirement based testing, performance, load, stress testing and usability testing. System testing is to be performed by independent team as independent testers see other and different defects and are unbiased. Faults found during system testing can be very expensive to fix. Performance & Usability is a non functional quality characteristic in testing.

In usability testing, the tester determines whether the client finds the system user friendly and attractive, and the extent to which the product is understood, simple to operate.

Integration / interface testing involves testing interaction between modules and sub-systems. Integration testing is testing the system when combined with other systems. It tests combined parts of application like units, modules, interfaces, individual applications, clients and servers, to determine whether they correctly function together. Integration testing determines which modules to combine when, and how many at once. Integration testing is performed to expose defects in the interfaces and in the interaction between integrated components. Normally integration testing is automatically done without the tester paying special attention. Example:

The SMS module, contacts module are tested through feature interaction testing. Interface testing is of two approaches top down and bottom up.

System testing should investigate on both functional and non-functional requirements. User Acceptance testing is done based on the business perspective before the built is delivered to the clients. Expected outcomes should be predicted before a test is run. They are derived from a specification, not from the code and may include timing constraints such as response times.

Expected outcomes are not defined by the software's behavior. The user requirements is the best source of expected outcomes for UA test scripts. Expected contract and regulation testing is also a part of acceptance testing. Field testing is performed by the clients at their own location. Acceptance test cases are based on requirements and do not necessarily include regression testing. It uses the Agile test methodology. In Agile test methodology, the client gives an overview of the project, the manager give a prototype demo to the client. The client again gives a feedback to the manager or developer, and the developer builds another version of the same model. Here the changes are continuously incorporated in this project, so this is also called as the least cost model.

Exhaustive testing is a test approach in which testing comprises of all possible combinations of input parameters and preconditions using test cases to cover different classes of errors.

Exhaustive testing is impractical but possible

3.1. The Bug / Defect Life Cycle: *When reporting the faults found to the developers, testers should be polite, constructive, helpful, diplomatic, sensitive to the way that they may react to criticism. Besides, a tester should also be firm about insisting that the bug is not a “feature”, if it should be fixed. The tests should be run in the order of importance only.*

Phase I: Tester initially assigns status as 'New' to the defect. When a defect is assigned to a developer, then its status is changed to 'Assigned'. The project leader can change the status of the defect to either 'Not an issue/ Terminate' or 'Duplicate' or 'Fixed/ Resolved'.

Phase II: If the tester validates that the defect was fixed then the defect is closed by the tester and the status of the defect is changed to 'Removed' by the tester.

Phase III: The tester checks the status of the bug and validates. If the bug was not resolved, the tester re-opens the issue and again assigns the defect to the developer.

3.2. The Bug Tracking Life Cycle

This helps in logging bugs and has several phases.

Phase I: Tester finds the bug and these new bugs are entered in defect tracking tools like Bugzilla, Mantis, MS-Excel, MS- word etc.

Phase II: Project leader analyses bugs, assigns priority to them and passes it to the concerned developers.

Phase III: Developer fixes bug and changes their status to 'Fixed' along with 'Fixed' details. New version, with all fixtures, is released to Quality Control team.

Phase IV: Quality Control team or tester performs **regression test** and checks status of bugs fixed.

Phase V: Fixed bugs are closed and if defects reoccur, issues are reopened and again forwarded to developers.

Write Test Summary Reports based on the information gathered during testing, deciding what should be automated, to what degree and how, create the test specifications are the major tasks of a Test Lead / Leader. However, interaction with the test tool vendor to identify best ways to leverage test tool on the project, is not the work of a test lead.

3.3. Bug /Defect report format: The fields of defect report format are, Defect found, Defect Type, Classification (Critical / Minor/ Major), Status (New / Removed/ Assigned), Defect Removal Time, Stage at which defect was injected and removed.

3.4. Test Plan format

This is a document describing the details of the testing, like required scope, resources, testing approaches, schedule, testing methodologies and test cases to be designed (not types of test cases), are prepared during project planning stage. Reviewing the test basis (such as requirements, architecture, design and interface) is not a part of test plan. Analysis of Specifications is also not part of a high level test plan. High level test plan specifies functions not to be tested, environmental requirements and entry -exit criteria are a part of high level test plan.

However expected results are not specified in test plan. The format has the following information.

- i. Project Name
- ii. *Test items*
- iii. *Scope and risks involved*
- iv. Estimated effort in person-months or person-hours
- v. *Test schedules & deadlines* - Estimated start date and end date, actual start date and end date

Allocation of resources - Test set up/ testware (test cases & test data set) including hardware and software environment and peripherals required, test data and test script, any special tool or equipment required, test personnel and their respective responsibility. Maintaining the operating system configuration that has been used in the test cycle, test documentation, user

requirements documentation is part of Configuration management. Tools like change Man, Clear case are used as configuration management tool. Status accounting of configuration items, identification of test versions and controlled library access are all a part of configuration management. However, configuration management system does not provide facilities to compare test results with expected results. Testware needs configuration management just like requirements, design and code. Configuration identification requires all CI's and their versions in the system. Configuration control maintains of CI's in a library. Configuration auditing checks on the contents of the library, Status reporting is function of recording and tracking problems. The test environment should be similar to the product environment. An effective software environment should have ease of use, capacity for incremental implementation and capability of evolving with the needs of a project. Incremental testing approach uses top down, bottom up and functional incrimination. A project manager has been transferred to a major software development project that is in the implementation phase. The highest priority for this project manager should be to establish a relationship with the customer, establish a relationship with the customer.

To test a function, the programmer has to write a driver (also called 'test harness' or 'scaffolding'), which calls the function to be tested and passes it test data.

- vi. *Levels of testing* i.e. Types of testing to be carried out including functional testing, structural testing, α - testing, β –testing, Gorilla testing, usability testing, performance testing, stress testing etc.
- vii. For each testing technique & strategy, *features to be tested and features not to be tested* i.e. test cases, test schedule and test management tools have to be specified. *A software*

engineer identifies, evaluates and ranks the tools and recommends the tools to the management.

- viii. *Test design techniques: The main purpose is to identify test conditions from requirement specifications and selecting test cases. Error guessing supplements formal rigorous test design techniques.*
- ix. *Defect reporting format is specified. However quality plans and incident reports are not specified. Defect arrival rate curve, shows the number of newly discovered defects per unit time.*
- x. *Exit criteria & deliverables: The purpose of exit criteria is to define when to stop testing, denote the end of test level, to notate that a specific pre condition has been achieved by a set of test. Checking test logs against the exit criteria specified in test planning, undertaking thoroughness measures , such as coverage of code, functionality or risk, making estimates of defect density or reliability measures, residual risk such as defects not fixed or lack of test coverage in certain areas, assessing if more tests are needed and writing a test summary report for stakeholders are major tasks of exit criteria checking. However, verifying the Test environment and logging the outcome of test execution is not a part of exit criteria. Deliverables does not include test summary report. Test execution provides the biggest potential cost saving from use of CAST.*

3.5. Testability

Testability is how easily computer programs can be tested. It tests for operability, observability, controllability, simplicity and understandability. In system development life cycle, requirements are translated to specifications, through which the code is developed. Once

construction is over, the product goes through various stages of testing before the final release.

Example: Response time should be less than 1 second for the specified design load.

3.5.1. Traceability matrix: There are several matrices to measure test availability. Requirement tracing is the process of documenting links between user requirements for the system we are building and work-product to be implemented. This helps in areas of Requirement management, Change management and Defect management. Complete list of details to be tested is prepared using traceability matrix before any test cases are written.

4. Some important testing techniques:

I. Web Specific Testing:

What are the key features to be concentrated upon when doing a testing for world wide web sites interaction between html pages, performance on the client side security aspects. Due to more complex user interface, technical issues and compatibility combinations, testing effort required for web application is considerably larger than that for application without any web interface. Web testing includes tests that are defined without interface and several web specific tests like compatibility testing. *Compatibility testing* determines if an application is performing as expected with various combinations of hardware and software. This includes testing of different browsers like Netscape Navigator, Internet Explorer and their various releases for *browser compatibility testing*, different types of operating system like Windows 95, Windows 98, Windows 2000, Windows NT, Unix, Linux, different monitor resolution like color resolution, font settings, display settings etc.

Compatibility testing can also include testing of different hardware configurations like PC, laptop and other hand held devices, different Internet connections like proxy server, firewalls, modems etc, desktop items like display, sound and video.

II. Security Testing:

Security testing falls under compliance testing. It determines ability of application to resist unauthorized system entry or modification. Security tester plays the role of individual penetrating or attacking the system. It verifies whether proper protection mechanisms are built in the system and is accomplished through the following.

- a) *Audit:* Ensures that all products installed in the site are secured when checked against known vulnerabilities.
- b) *Attacking:* Attacking the server through vulnerabilities in network infrastructure.
- c) *Hacking:* Hacking directly through website and HTML code.
- d) *Cookies attack:* Finding patterns in cookies and attempting to create algorithm.

III. Functional testing for web applications

Functional testing is not to check whether the system performs functions within specified response times. It is testing the end to end functionality of the system as a whole. This includes all types of tests listed in general testing in addition to link testing. Link testing verifies that a link takes us to expected destination without failure. The link is not broken and all the parts of the site are connected. Links to be tested includes embedded links (underlying extension indicating that more stuff is available), structural link (links to a set of pages that are subordinate to the current page and reference link), associative link (additional links that may be of some interest to users). *In MASPAR case study, an error in the code was so obscure that you had to test the function with almost every input value to find its two special-case failures.*

IV. Static Testing

It includes verification or review of documentation, technology and code. It is a testing technique that does not execute code. Static testing is performed at the beginning of development life cycle

to detect and remove defects early in development and test cycle. It thus prevents migration of defects to later phases of development. This further improves communication with entire project development team. *Reviews, static analysis and dynamic testing have the same objective of identifying defects. There are basically four types of static testing – informal review, inspection, technical review and walkthrough. Informal review is not based on documentation procedure. Cost of the reviews will not include tool support. Success Factors for a review include that each review does not have a predefined objective, defects found are welcomed and expressed objectively and management supports a good review process. However in review there is no emphasis on learning and process improvement. Review should be performed on specifications, code and test plans. It is just an inexpensive way to get some benefits. Peer review also known as technical review, which has no management participation. FTR is a review conducted by trained moderator. The phases are planning, kick off meetings, individual preparations, review meetings, rework and follow-up from software metrics. In planning phase selecting the personnel and allocating roles to them but explaining the objectives is not part of review process. Moderator is the key person who mediates between people. Scribe/ Recorder is the person responsible for documenting all the issues, problems and open points that were identified during review meeting. Inspection is appropriate when there are written documents. In FTR, the managers can perform inspections on management documents. Analyzing metrics and improving processes, setting up forms and databases, time spent on the document outside the meeting are included in typical costs for an inspection process but not writing the documents to be inspected. In Inspection pre-meeting preparation is required. Inspection is done by a trained moderator or leader and uses entry exit criteria including metrics, while walkthrough is lead by an author. Scenario, Dry Run , Peer Group*

are key characteristics of Walk Through. Code review & code inspection are considered part of testing because both help detect faults and improve quality. Unreachable code can be best found using code reviews. Code inspection is a static test, which enables the code to be tested before the execution environment is ready. Error guessing is best used after more formal techniques have been applied. Error guessing supplements formal rigorous test design techniques. It is most appropriate way of deriving system tests. Procedures and standards are used to produce right output products. Procedures are step by step method followed to ensure that standards are met.

(Case: A person has been dominating current software process improvement meeting. In this case the facilitator should wait for the person to pause, acknowledge the person's opinion, and ask for someone else's opinion, to bring other team members into discussion.)

Dynamic Testing

At the end of development, dynamic testing validates whether client requirements are satisfied. It is a testing that executes code. The bulk of testing effort is dynamic testing.

Dynamic testing is of three types. Structure based testing ensures statement coverage, branch/condition coverage and decision coverage. Experience based testing is based on passed experience and error guessing ability. Existing system, individual knowledge and user manual forms Test oracle. The oracle assumption verifies whether a tester can routinely identify the correct outcome of a test. Specification based testing uses black box testing techniques.

Test coverage criteria can be measured in terms of items exercised by a test suite. A measure of the test coverage criteria is the percentage of user requirements covered and not on percentage of faults found. Test coverage criteria are often used when specifying test completion criteria. Coverage measurement is a partial measurement of test thoroughness. In

prioritizing what to test, the most important objective is to obtain good test coverage and test high risk areas. Risk analysis two major components taken into consideration - the probability that the negative event will occur and the potential loss or impact associated with the event. Deviations from standards, requirement defects, design defects, insufficient maintainability and incorrect interface specifications are typical defects that are easier to find in reviews than in dynamic testing.

(Case: A project that is in the implementation phase is six weeks behind schedule. The delivery date for the product is four months away. The project is not allowed to slip the delivery date or compromise on the quality standards established for this product. Eliminating some of the requirements that have not yet been implemented would bring this project back on schedule.)

VI. Concurrency Testing

This technique is followed when there are multiple clients with same server and ensures that server can handle simultaneous requests from clients.

VII. Parallel Testing

This is a testing technique performed by using same data to run both old and new system.

VIII. Client Server Testing

Application function tests, server tests, database tests and network communication tests are commonly conducted on client server architecture in three different levels. In first level, individual client applications are tested in 'disconnected mode' and operations of server and underlying network are not considered. In second level, though network operations are not tested, client software and server applications are tested. In third level, complete client server architecture is tested.

IX. Load Testing

Here we subject the target of the test, to varying workloads to measure and evaluate the performance behaviors and ability of the target and of the test to continue to function properly under these different workloads for ensuring that system can handle extended work loaded. Load testing tools reduces the time spent by the testers, reduces the resources spent (hardware) and are mostly used in web testing. It verifies that running large number of concurrent clients do not break connection with server or /and client software. Loading is steadily increased until system failure. It discovers deadlock and problem with queries.

X. Stress Testing

Subjecting a system to unreasonable amount of work load, while it denies resources like RAM, disks etc to determine the break point of the system. It checks system for robustness to determine whether it can continue to operate in adverse situations demanding resources in abnormal frequency, quantity or volume. *Stress testing is not a unit test standard.*

XI. Performance testing

Performance testing can be done during unit testing, as well as during the testing of whole system. Performance testing helps in measuring the response time, transaction rates, generating many transactions and also simulating many users. White box tester is not responsible for checking for the performance of an application.

XI. Gray Box testing

It is partially white box and partially black box testing, as it is related to coding as well as specification.

XII. Code / Unit / Component Testing

Behavioral and Structural testing is a part of unit testing. A common testing during component testing is statement and branch testing. Path testing ensures execution of all possible control flow of path through the program and we can achieve 100% coverage. Data flow analysis is the use of data on paths through the code. It is the rate of change of data values as a program executes. It is stated that the minimum test state that achieves 100% path/branch coverage will also achieve 100% statement coverage. 100% branch coverage guarantees 100% decision coverage and also 100% decision coverage guarantees 100% branch coverage. LCSAJ (Linear Code Sequence and Jump) coverage is 100% decision coverage and is not a black box testing technique. A minimal test set that achieves 100% path coverage will generate detect more faults than one that achieves 100% statement coverage. Statement testing executes all statements in the program at least once. Statement coverage tests for unused branches, unused statement and dead code but not missing statements. Checking memory leaks and robustness are also a part of component testing. Static and dynamic analysis tools are used by developer's team. Static analysis, analyzes the program code but compiling code is not a form of static analysis. Static analysis checks for the use of a variable before it has been defined, unreachable ("dead") code and array bound violations. Defects discovered by static analysis tools include variables that are never used, security vulnerabilities, programming standard violations and uncalled functions and procedures. Dynamic analysis is a tool for detecting memory leak as static analysis cannot find them. . Dynamic analysis tool will be used to test the flag memory leaks and unassigned pointers. The extent to which the software can be used in other applications is software re-usability.

Path testing: This testing technique helps in selecting a set of paths through the program. A path through a program is a sequence and a specific combination of conditions, instructions or

statements that starts at any junction or decision and ends at another, which is handled by the program.

Branch testing/Arc Testing executes enough test cases to assure that every branch has been exercised at least once under some tests.

Functional testing: Every program operates on finite number of inputs. For each input, the routine either accepts the stream and produces a correct outcome or accepts the stream and produces an incorrect outcome or rejects the stream and tells that it did so.

Structural testing: One should execute enough test cases to ensure that every path through the routine should be exercised at least once. Pure structural testing cannot ensure us that the routine is doing the right thing. Example: Some loops may not terminate.

Correctness Proof: This relies on the combination of structural and functional testing.

Defect Testing: It has got two objectives ensuring that system specifications are met and defects are exposed.

Black box testing / Functional testing / Behavioral testing

It ensures that functional requirements and specifications of clients are fulfilled. Test cases are generated to evaluate system correctness. It is “testing by looking at requirements to develop test cases”. It simulates actual system users and makes no assumption on system structure. However, it has potential of missing logical errors and involves possibility of redundant testing. A black box tester should be highly motivated to find faults, he should be able to understand the functional requirements specification and also be creative to

Functional testing uses models like process flow model, state transaction model and plain language specification model. Stochastic testing using statistical information or operational

profiles uses Model based testing approach. Operation testing is ease of operation of the software. FPA is used to measure the size of functionality of an Information system.

Black box or Functional testing can be done using state transitions, equivalence partitioning, BVA, use case testing and decision table. State transition is a non-functional test. Non-functional testing will you perform on internet banking solution. A field failure occurs when multiple users access system. This indicates an important non-functional requirement was not specified and tested. Decision testing is not a functional testing. Use case testing is done to test business scenario. Use cases are most useful in uncovering defects in the “process flows” through a system based on its real world use. Security testing is a functional testing that investigates the functions relating to detection of threats, such as virus from malicious outsiders. Functional testing is used more than structural testing.

White Structural testing / Glass box testing

It ensures that technical and house keeping functions of the system works. Test cases are designed to verify that system structure is sound enough and can perform intended task. It is “testing by looking at the program skeleton”. Exclusive use of white box testing in a test-phase will run the risk that the requirements are not satisfied. We can test structural logic of software and statements. However, it does not ensure that user requirements are fulfilled. These tests may not be applicable in real world situation.

Maintenance Testing is a type of software maintenance: This is neither a type nor a level of testing, rather a maintenance type. Impact analysis helps in analyzing how much regression testing is to be done. Maintenance Testing uses impact Analysis the most. Breadth testing is a test suite that exercises the full functionality of a product but does not test features in detail. Depth testing is a test that exercises a feature of a product in full detail. Maintenance testing

includes testing some features in detail (for e.g. environment) and for some features detail testing is not required. It's a mix of both breadth and depth testing. Maintenance testing is done on a released system that has been changed. After deployment of the system, it is often in service for years. The user can find unexpected behavior during its service or may suggest some modifications in the service due to changes in operating environment. Maintenance releases and technical assistance centers are examples of external failure in costs of quality. Scalability is not a software characteristic.

Equivalence partitioning *Equivalence class: A black box test design technique achieves input and output coverage, in which test cases are designed to execute representatives from equivalence partitions. It is an input or output range of values such that only one value in the range becomes a test case. For e.g. input a valid class contains values from 3-5, then any value between 3-5 is considered as an input. All values are supposed to yield same output. Hence one value in this range becomes a test case. In principle, test cases are designed to cover each partition at least once. When testing a grade calculation system, a tester determines that all scores from 90 to 100 will yield a grade of A, but scores below 90 will not. This analysis is known as Equivalence partitioning.*

Boundary value analysis: *Boundary value is an input value or output value that is on the edge of an equivalence partition. It tests boundary conditions on, below and above the edges of input and output equivalence classes. Example: minimum and maximum value of a range. BVA is a black box testing technique, in which test cases are designed based on boundary values.*

Example: Order numbers on a stock control system can range between 10000 and 99999 inclusive. Which of the following inputs might be a result of designing tests for only valid equivalence classes and valid boundaries. (Ans: 10000, 50000, 99999)

How many minimum test cases should be written?

1. (a)

SWITCH PC on

Start "Outlook"

If Outlook appears THEN

Send an email // test case for statement coverage and test case for branch coverage

Close outlook // branch coverage test

Ans: 1 for statement coverage, 2 for branch coverage.

2. IF A > B THEN

C = A - B // Branch 1

ELSE

C = A + B // Branch 2

END IF

READ D // statement 1

IF C = D THEN

PRINT "ERROR" //Statement 2 (No need of branch coverage as statement already covers it

END IF ***(Ans: 2 for statement coverage, 2 for branch coverage.)***

1. (b) Given the following code, which statement is true about the minimum number of test cases required for full statement and branch coverage?

```
Read p
Read q
IF p+q > 100 THEN
Print "Large"
ENDIF
IF p > 50 THEN
Print "p Large"
ENDIF
```

(Ans: 1 test for statement coverage, 2 for branch coverage)

3. Analyze the following highly simplified procedure. Decide the minimum number of tests that are needed to ensure that all the questions have been asked, all combinations occurred and all replies are given.

Ask: "What type of ticket do you require? (Single/ Return)"

If the customer wants 'Return'

 Ask "What rate? (Standard/ Cheap-Day)"

 If the customer replies "Cheap-Day"

 Say: "That will be \$11.20"

 Else

 Say: "That will be \$19.50"

 End If

 Else

 Say: "That will be \$9.75"

End If

Ans: 3

4. A program validates a numeric field as follows: Values less than 10 are rejected, values between 10 and 21 are accepted, values greater than or equal to 22 are rejected. What input values cover all the equivalence partitions? What input covers the most boundary values?

Ans: (i) 3,10, 22 (ii) 9,10,21,22

5. In a system designed to work out the tax to be paid: An employee has Rs.4000 of salary tax free. The next Rs.1500 is taxed at 10%. The next Rs. 28,000 is taxed at 40%. To the nearest whole Rs., which of this is a valid BVA test case? Which of these groups of numbers would fall into the same equivalence class?

Ans: i) Up to 4000 → 0%, 4001 to 5500 → 10%, 5501 -33500 →22%, 33501 - ... →40%

ii) \$5800; \$28000; \$32000

6. An input field that takes year of birth between 1900 and 2004. The Boundary values for testing this field are 1899, 2900,2004,2005

7. How many test cases are necessary to cover all the possible sequences of statements (paths) for the following program fragment?

if (Condition 1) then statement 1 else statement 2;

if (Condition 2) then statement 3.....

Ans: 2 Test Cases

8. If the pseudo code below were a programming language ,how many tests are required to achieve 100% statement coverage and how many tests are required to achieve 100% branch/decision coverage?

1.If x=3 then

2. Display_messageX;

3. If y=2 then
4. Display_messageY;
5. Else
6. Display_messageZ;
- 7.Else
8. Display_messageZ;

Ans: 3 for 100% statement coverage and 2 for 100% branch coverage.

9. One of the fields on a form contains a text box which accepts alpha numeric values. Identify the Valid Equivalence class. **Ans: Boo01k**

10. The Switch is switched off once the temperature falls below 18 and then it is turned on when the temperature is more than 21. Identify the Equivalence values which belong to the same class.

We first divide the classes, but **not** in to valid or invalid classes. **Ans: 22,23,24**

Class I: less than 18 (switch turned off)

Class II: 18 to 21

Class III: above 21 (switch turned on)

10. What is the smallest number of test cases required to Provide 100% branch coverage?

If(x>y) x=x+1; else y=y+1; while(x>y) {y=x*y; x=x+1; } **Ans: 2**

11. If a candidate is given an exam of 40 questions, should get 25 marks to pass (61%) and should get 80% for distinction, what is equivalence class. **Ans: 32,37,40**

12. One of the fields on a form contains a text box which accepts alphabets in lower or upper case. Identify the invalid Equivalence class value. **Ans :_CLa01ss**

13. **What is the expected result for each of the following test cases?**

	Rule 1	Rule 2	Rule 3	Rule 4
Conditions				
Citibank Card Member	Yes	Yes	No	No
Type of Room	Silver	Platinum	Silver	Platinum
Actions				
Offer upgrade to Gold Luxury	Yes	No	No	No
Offer upgrade to Silver	N/A	Yes	N/A	No

A. Citibank card member, holding a Silver room

B. Non Citibank-member, holding a Platinum room

Ans: A – Offer upgrade to Gold, B – Don't offer any upgrade.

14. Minimum Test Required for Statement Coverage :-

Disc = 0; Order-qty = 0

Read Order-qty

If Order-qty >=20 then Disc = 0.05

If Order-qty >=100 then Disc =0.1 End if

End if

Ans. Statement coverage is 1

Levels of testing

There are different levels of testing used in the testing process, each level of testing used in the testing process, aims to test different aspects of the system.

The basic levels are unit testing for the first level, integration testing for the second level, system testing for the third level and user acceptance testing for the fourth level.

6. Testing Life cycle

The stages in testing life cycle are as follows:

- Corresponding to test strategy, the test strategy review is done.

- Corresponding to test plan and specification, review of test plan and specification is done.
- After test execution, quality review is done. *Test implementation and execution includes creating test suites, executing and comparing results. The incident record includes information on test environments. The final stage of incident tracking is not fixing. An incident may be closed without being fixed. Incidents should always be investigated and resolved. Incidents cannot be analyzed to assist in test process. Reporting Discrepancies as incidents is a part of test execution and implementation phase. Incident is reporting discrepancies, in other terms its defect/bug. The structure of an incident report is called as Anomaly report. We find defects while execution cycle where we execute the test cases.*
- After defect reporting and closure, defect reporting review is performed.
- On receiving test results, test result review is done.
- Corresponding to final inspection, the final inspection and quality review is done.
- Finally we have product delivery.

7. Test Cases Design

Select test cases → Execute test cases → Analyze test results

Test cases are systematically designed to uncover different error classes with minimum amount of time and effort. *Test cases are devised as set of data with the intent of determining whether system processes them correctly.*

Test cases are defined as “A set of input parameters for which the software will be tested”.

Test cases are selected, programs are executed and results are compared with estimated results.

Test cases have to be designed based on two criteria, - *Reliability* and *Validity*. *A set of test cases is considered to be reliable if it detects all errors and unlikely to cause a failure. A fault need not affect the reliability of a system.* A set of test cases is considered to be valid, if at least one test case reveals error. At times, *there are several risks of managing your project's schedule with a statistical reliability model. These include testers spend more energy early in the product trying to find bugs than preparing to do the rest of the project's work more efficiently, managers might not realize that the testing effort is ineffective, late in the project, because they expect a low rate of bug finding, so the low rate achieved doesn't alarm them. It can increase the end-of-project pressure on testers to not find bugs, or to not report bugs.* We can develop test cases using the *Black Box* and *White Box* testing techniques.

Test case specification document / Test Case Design format is given below.

1. Requirement Id.
2. TestCaseId./TestNo.
3. Test item description.
4. Pre-Condition/Pre-Requisition
5. Input Action / Test Action
6. Test case description/purpose
7. Expected Results: *Tests are most effective when specified in advance, before execution.*
8. Actual Results
9. Comments/Remark
10. Bug Id

Test cases are designed during test specification. Test cases designed by a person from a different organization have highest level of independence. Incidents occur when expected

and actual results differ. Incidents are analyzed to assist in test improvement procedure. Incident can be raised against requirements, documents and test cases but not against improvements suggested by users. An incident logging system provides valuable source of information during testing, if it contains all project related incidents. Incidents require investigation and/ or correction. Incidents can also be raised against documentation or as per user requirements.

8. Types of testing documents

There are generally three types of test documents. *Plan Documents* (Project, Quality and SCM plan), *Input Output Documents* (Requirement Specification, High Level Design, Low Level Design), *Deliverables* (User Manuals, Installation and customization guide).

9. Testing as a validation strategy

Validation checks “*Are we building the product right?*” Validation strategy includes Unit Testing, Integration Testing, System testing, Performance testing, α – testing, User acceptance testing, Installation testing and β – testing. Generally verification testing finds 20% of total bugs while validation testing finds 80% of total bugs by ‘*Pareto*’ principle. Independent verification and validation is done by entity outside the project’s sphere of influence. Early verification reduces defect multiplication. Verification activities always include testers. Software verification and validation program provides management with insights into the state of a software project. It is executed in parallel with software development activities.

10. When is testing complete?

The best definition of complete testing is “you have reached the scheduled ship date.” Actually testing should be stopped when the required amount of confidence has been achieved and also depending on the risk of the software project for the industry, business product supplier issues,

legal requirements, contract, technical issues and special requirements to be tested. However it does not depend on test data. Organizational factors are a project risk and not product risk. Poor software characteristics, error prone software delivered and software that does not perform its intended function are only product risks. In a risk-based approach the risks identified may be used to determine the test technique to be employed, the extent of testing to be carried out and also prioritize testing in an attempt to find critical defects as early as possible. However, the risk identified is not used to determine the cost of the project. In case of large systems, Testing should be on the basis of risk. Important consequences of the impossibility of complete testing are that we can never be certain that the program is bug free, we have no definite stopping point for testing, which makes it easier for some managers to argue for very little testing, we have no easy answer for what testing tasks should always be required, because every task takes time that could be spent on other high importance tasks. A test manager is responsible for conducting test readiness review. A test manager who wants to use the resources available for the automated testing of a web application. The best choice is tester, test automater, web specialist and a DBA.

The criteria for determining completion of testing are as follows:

- i. When we run out of time or money.
- ii. Based on statistical criteria and bug rate falls below certain level.
- iii. Test budget is depleted or the deadline is reached for releasing the software.
- iv. Test cases are completed with certain percentage.
- v. **Code coverage is the measure of defects.** Code coverage or functionality requirement reaches specific point.
- vi. α - testing or β –testing period ends.

11. V – Model, an effective test methodology in industries

Phase I: In Requirement gathering phase, user acceptance test plan is prepared.

Phase II: Functional specification is prepared and system test plan is designed.

Phase III: Design phase has corresponding integration test plan.

Phase IV: Program specification stage, where high level design and low level design are made and code and unit test report is generated.

We have all test plans prepared and accordingly all tests are done based on defined phase wise tests, which needs to be done till project implementation. *V-model includes verification of designs.*

Conclusion: Good testing techniques find maximum uncovered errors. Success of testing depends on selecting appropriate combination of testing techniques, developing test conditions, test evaluation criteria, creating test script required to test rest of the above conditions, managing fixes and re-testing and need to meet rest of the testing objectives.